

INTERACTIVE METHODS IN DEVELOPING YOUNG LEARNERS' SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract

In this article, the development of speech skills. The article aims to analyze the impact of interactive technologies on the motivation and fluency of young learners. Improving students' speaking skills. The article promotes the motivation of young students, expands their worldview, and helps create a comfortable learning environment.

Key words: Motivation, speaking skills, interactive technologies, methods, vocabulary, primary school.

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada nutq qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish. Maqola interaktiv texnologiyalarning ta'sir qilish usullarini tahlil qilishga qaratilgan motivatsiya va yosh o'quvchilarning ravongapirishgaundash. Talabalarni nutq qobiliyatini oshirish. Maqola yosh o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasi dunyo qarashini kengaytiradi qulay ta'lim muhitini yaratishga yordamberadi.

Kalitso'zlar: Motivatsiya, nutq qobiliyatlari, interaktiv texnologiyalar, usul, so'zboyligi, boshlang'ich sinf.

Аннотация

В этой статье развитие речевых навыков. Целью статьи является анализ влияния интерактивных технологий на мотивацию и беглость речи молодых учащихся. Улучшение разговорных навыков учащихся. Статья способствует мотивации молодых студентов, расширяет их мировоззрение, помогает создать комфортную среду обучения.

Ключевые слова: Мотивация, разговорные навыки, интерактивные технологии, методы, словарный запас, начальная школа.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, great attention is paid to the development of speech skills among pupils and students. The main principle of speech learning is to improve the listening and listening skills of young learners and students.

By considering all ideas, interactive methods are the most effective tool in developing young learners' speaking skills since it helps to create comfortable

environment of teaching process and it leads to stimulating young learners' activities. Besides in interactive methods teacher encourages learners to search for information independently, to interact with readiness and enthusiasm in communicative situations.

The main task of developing the speech of a preschool child is to master the norms and rules of the mother tongue for each age stage and to develop his communicative abilities. It should be noted that the speech level of children of the same age can be completely different from each other. Speech development (acquisition of the mother tongue) in preschool age is a multifaceted process by its nature. It is inextricably linked with intellectual development, because the developed thinking of a person is speech, language, and logical thinking. The interrelationship between speech development, language acquisition and the development of intelligence and knowledge shows how important language is for the development of thinking. Especially in the formation of fluent speech, that is, meaningful, logical, coherent speech, the organic connection between speech and intellectual development is more obvious.

In recent years, much attention has been paid to the study of some stages in the development of speech. It is known that every person improves his speech throughout his life by acquiring linguistic resources. Each age stage brings something new to his speech development.

For speech activity, as well as for the development of students' speech, it is necessary to observe several conditions:

1. There must be a requirement for human speech to emerge. The methodical requirement of developing students' speech is to create a situation in which the student expresses his opinion, the desire and need to express something verbally and in writing.
2. Any speech should have content and material. The more complete, rich, and valuable this material is, the more meaningful its description will be.
3. An idea is understandable only if it is expressed using words, phrases, sentences, and turns of speech that the listener understands. Therefore, the third condition for successful development of speech is arming speech with language tools.

There are several aspects of speech acquisition.

1. Learning the norms of the literary language.
2. Mastering the important speaking skills that every member of our society needs, i.e. reading and writing skills
3. Improving students' speech culture.

Three directions are clearly distinguished in the development of speech: 1) working on words; 2) working on phrases and sentences; 3) work on connected speech.

The most important stages of acquiring speech correspond to preschool age. Based on this, special attention is currently being paid to the study of some stages in the development of speech. Scientists have realized that the pre-speech stage plays an important role and are analyzing it in detail.

It should be noted that a teacher working with children deal with so-called mixed-ability groups. That is why a teacher has to take into consideration multiple intelligences of students: different types of personality, thinking, scope of attention, the ability to perceive and process information. (Korovina, Pushkina, & Krivoshlykova, 2017, p.10).

To promote students' communicative competence and to make lessons more purposeful and interactive such activities as simulation and role-play are to be employed as they contribute to students' considering themselves as much real as possible (Ahmed & Pawar, 2018, p.309).

Foreign language teachers should be accurate in designing learner-friendly, "supportive and nurturing" educational environment and help pupils "become confident and enthusiastic communicators" ("Five Components ...", 2014, p.42).

On this account, Carmen Becker and Jana Roos (2016) stick to the point that "creative speaking activities in the young learners' classroom act can provide a springboard for speaking in the early language classroom" (p.21).

The article aims to analyze the ways interactive technologies influence motivation and encourage young learners to speak fluently. To achieve this, it is necessary to take into account the difficulties of students in speaking fluently. In this context, vocabulary is vital and needs to be further developed for use in the learning process.

1. Role-play activities: Encourage young learners to take on different roles and engage in conversations with their peers. This can help them practice speaking in various situations and develop their confidence.

2. Storytelling: Encourage young learners to tell stories or create their own narratives. This can help them practice organizing their thoughts and expressing themselves fluently.

3. Show and tell: Allow young learners to bring in an item from home and talk about it in front of the class. This can help them practice speaking in front of an audience and improve their descriptive language skills.

4. Pair work and group discussions: Organize activities where young learners work in pairs or small groups to discuss a topic or solve a problem. This can help them practice speaking and listening to their peers.
5. Language games: Incorporate fun and interactive language games that require young learners to speak and interact with each other. This can make speaking practice more enjoyable and engaging for them.
6. Using technology: Integrate technology such as educational apps, interactive whiteboards, or online platforms to engage young learners in speaking activities. This can make speaking practice more dynamic and appealing to tech-savvy students.
7. Drama and performances: Organize drama activities or performances where young learners have the opportunity to speak and act out different roles. This can help them develop their speaking skills while also boosting their confidence and creativity.
8. Real-life simulations: Create scenarios that mimic real-life situations, such as ordering food at a restaurant or asking for directions. This can help young learners practice speaking in practical contexts and improve their communication skills.

Children are shy to express their thoughts and ideas within the school lesson and these methods help them to speak freely and reveal less shyness and self-fluency.

CONCLUSION

Special lesson skills are developed for success in speaking fluency. Fluent speech based on the interactive method proposed in the article increases the enthusiasm of young students and students, expands their worldview, helps to create a comfortable speaking atmosphere, and as a result, they have the ability to think independently and think.

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